

Request for Information – Evaluation Project

Contact: Name, Organization
Date of Issue: Date
Deadline for submissions: 4:00pm Eastern Time, Date

1. Introduction

This RFI is a request by CLIENT for a qualified respondent (“Respondent”) to submit Responses (“Responses”) to help the Client select an Evaluator for the NAME OF PROGRAM. This RFI does not represent a call for tenders and does not bind CLIENT and does not constitute an offer of any kind by CLIENT to any or all Respondents.

This RFI will result in the selection of a contractor who is expected to provide the following Evaluation Services to CLIENT.

YEAR ONE:

- The revision of a draft Program Manual and evaluation framework to incorporate feedback from expert reviewers, PROGRAM-NAME team members, and members of the Advisory Committee (DATE)
- The revision, development and pilot testing of data collection tools and measures for PROGRAM-NAME (DATE TO DATE)
- The collection and analysis of data from PROGRAM-NAME (continuous feedback to the program)
- The recommendation of changes to program design and implementation based on the first year's evaluation (DATE)
- Revision of data collection tools, measures and analytic framework (DATE)

YEARS TWO TO FOUR:

- Ongoing data collection, analysis and feedback to the program

- Delivery of an annual evaluation report that recommends changes to the program

YEAR FIVE:

- Ongoing data collection, analysis and feedback to the program
- Delivery of a final evaluation report that summarizes the outcomes of the program and makes recommendations for further research and programming
- Engagement in knowledge transfer with Canadian decision-makers

2. Project Background

2.1 *About CLIENT*

[Write description of CLIENT organization]

2.2 *About PROGRAM-NAME*

[Write description of program in enough detail to give the evaluators a feel for its scope, structure and complexity.]

2.3 *Project Context and Sources of Information*

The Evaluator will be expected to work with staff and contractors of CLIENT to develop an integrated evaluation framework and performance measurement system that will improve the program on an ongoing basis as well as evaluating impact and cost effectiveness for the final report.

Because of the requirement to work with other elements of CLIENT's program, we are not requesting a full-fledged proposal at this point. The details of any evaluation plan will be subject to changes as we jointly figure out how to use data cost-effectively.

CLIENT will be collecting a great deal of information as part of program delivery, some of which is summarized below. Staff of CLIENT will be responsible for developing many of these data collection instruments, and the Respondent would work with him/her to ensure that the data will be helpful for evaluation purposes. In addition, the Evaluator will be expected to work within the emerging evaluation framework for the CLIENT, which includes program quality as measured by.... .

The Evaluator is expected to minimize the cost and intrusiveness of data collection as much as possible by taking advantage of the overall information system. For example, the Evaluator may recommend revisions to data definitions on the intake form to make administrative data more useful for evaluation and develop rubrics for the qualitative analysis of content that is developed as a natural part of program delivery (e.g., journal entries, stories, web analytics).

The Evaluator may provide guidance via teleconferences to PROGRAM-NAME staff on how to collect high quality data (for example, how to interview youth and their families). We expect to minimize the need for Evaluator travel by creating a dataset that is primarily derived from the activities of the

program and/or collected by program staff.

The following data will be collected as part of the web site, CLIENT administrative procedures and program implementation.

Web metrics

The web site will allow CLIENT to track and collect data / metrics on engagement and participation in the program and website. PROGRAM-NAME will probably use Google Analytics, a free online service that tracks web activity on the PROGRAM-NAME site, external and internal referrals, and so on. The specific data collected will depend on the web design.

Online surveys

PROGRAM-NAME will use survey software (TBC) for its data collection forms that can be downloaded in csv format and used for program feedback as well as evaluation.

Administrative data

CLIENT is adopting NAME OF SOFTWARE IF APPLICABLE to collect data on Club activities including enrollment, attendance and other activities. Data will be available in csv format.

Other forms and surveys

Draft forms are included in the appendix to the Program Manual.

2.4 Project Timing

- RFI Issued –
- Submissions Due –
- Selection of short list candidates – Week of
- Contract Decision –
- Start of Work -

2.4 Project Deliverables

The Evaluator will be responsible for working with staff and contractors of CLIENT to provide the following:

- Revision of the Program Manual and Evaluation Framework (DATE)
- Development of a multi-year evaluation plan (DATE)
- Revision or development of data collection instruments and measures that, whenever possible, can be gathered unobtrusively or as an integrated part of program implementation

(DATE)

- Frequent analysis and feedback to program staff regarding youth and mentor satisfaction, suggestions for improvements, and other useful program data (Monthly or as appropriate)
- Annual report that evaluates the program and provides recommendations for the upcoming year (MONTH AND YEARS)
- Final report that evaluates the impact and cost effectiveness of the program and makes policy recommendations for CLIENT, funders and other programs. (DATE)

2.5 Budget

The budget range for this project is expected to be between \$85,000 to \$100,000 per year for up to five years, inclusive of all expenses and exclusive of HST. Some years may require more cost than others depending on the evaluation plan.

The Evaluator is responsible for managing scope of work to fit within the overall budget. Changes to project scope and budget may be negotiated between the Evaluator and CLIENT as long as it is confirmed in writing by both parties.

3. Respondent Qualifications:

This RFI is open only to Respondents who have been pre-qualified on the basis of a screening process that was carried out in DATE.

On April 13, an invitation to submit Expressions of Interest (see Appendix) was posted on the project opportunities board of the Canadian Evaluation Society, distributed to the YouthMentoring listserv, and emailed to several Evaluators known to CLIENT.

Out of xx Expressions of Interest, CLIENT selected xx applicants to receive a Request for Information based on the following criteria:

- Research, evaluation and/or policy expertise in the relevant subject areas
- Prominence and credibility in the relevant subject areas
- A commitment to and demonstrated engagement in knowledge transfer

4. Submission Requirements

4.1 Content and Format of Responses

The Response should be submitted by email with the following attachments:

- A Word document with the following sections:
 - A filled-out Response Template (section 7)

- Your comments on the draft Statement of Work (section 9) with suggested revisions or suggestions reflecting your approach to the Evaluation. At this point your suggestions will not be treated as a proposal, but may be discussed during contract negotiations
- Resumes or CVs of two or three consultants/researchers who will be the main people involved in the project
- A description of the background and experience of your organizational entity (an excerpt of the 'About Us' web page is fine)
- The draft Program Manual (to be attached to this RFI) with your tracked changes. Comments may be informal, as feedback between colleagues, and will not be shared in their raw state beyond CLIENT staff and contractors working on PROGRAM-NAME.
- Two relevant reports authored by the Respondent in Word or PDF. This could be the same or different from the reports referenced in the Expression of Interest. They should demonstrate the qualifications and experience of the Respondent in relation to PROGRAM-NAME.

4.2 *Use of Responses*

The responses will be carefully reviewed, and comments may be incorporated into future versions of the Program Manual and/or evaluation framework and/or other program content. By submitting your response, you are agreeing to CLIENT's use of any and all of your comments regarding the Program Manual and evaluation framework.

Individual comments and changes will not be attributed to individual contributors. Please do not include any comments or information in your notes to the Program Manual, Evaluation Framework or Statement of Work that you do not wish us to use as input to the program. All compliant respondents to this RFI will be acknowledged as 'External Reviewers' in the Program Manual unless they request to be left out of the list.

Your thoughtful comments are most appreciated, and we believe that feedback from this highly qualified group of Respondents will make a valuable contribution to the youth served by the program.

4.3 *Submission Instructions*

Responses to this Request for Information should be submitted to CONTACT-NAME on or before **4:00pm ET on DATE** via email at CONTACT-EMAIL. We suggest that you cc: the email to yourself and/or follow up with a voice message to CONTACT-NAME AND PHONE NUMBER to ensure that the email has gone through.

4.3 *Questions and Communication*

Respondents are encouraged to seek clarification on any matters that it requires assistance with. Any questions regarding this RFI should be directed to CONTACT-NAME by email at CONTACT-

EMAIL, no later than three business days before submission deadline, but the earlier the better. You are welcome to contact Neil more than once, as questions arise.

In CLIENT's discretion, where it determines that questions and the answers to such questions should be shared with all Respondents, CLIENT will distribute the questions and answers to all Respondents.

5. Evaluation of Responses

The purpose of the RFI is to reach a shortlist of 2-3 Respondents to be invited to refine and negotiate a Statement of Work and contract.

The selection criteria when reviewing the Responses will be as follows.

- A compliant response is submitted by the stated deadline (Mandatory)
- Feedback on the draft Program Manual and evaluation framework is insightful and helpful, showing an understanding of the objectives of PROGRAM-NAME and the mission of CLIENT (10 points)
- Recommendations and comments on the draft Statement of Work show a capacity to provide a cost-effective and valuable contribution to PROGRAM-NAME (5 points)
- The Respondent has shown that it has access to consulting resources at costs that will support a qualified team to deliver a high quality project within the maximum budget (5 points)
- The Respondent has demonstrated through reports, resumes and references that it has successfully delivered similar projects in the past (5 points)
- The Respondent demonstrates a good fit with the mission and culture of CLIENT (5 points)

In the following and final stage of selection, the two or three shortlisted Respondents will be contacted by CLIENT to discuss and revise a Statement of Work and negotiate contract conditions. The contract decision will be based on:

- The extent to which the Respondent's proposed Statement of Work and price provides the best value for CLIENT
- The Respondent's demonstrated project management practices (i.e., a proven history of submitting deliverables according to agreed milestones, managing scope while being responsive to changes in the situation, and backup plans in case of consultant turnover in the x years of the project.)
- The extent to which communications with the Respondent throughout the entire process demonstrate that the Respondent would be a supportive, challenging and valuable partner for CLIENT and PROGRAM-NAME.

- The Respondent's demonstrated ability and willingness to engage in knowledge transfer beyond the scope of the actual evaluation activities (e.g., communicating the research findings to Canadian decision-makers).

Respondents not awarded the work outlined here will be notified by email.

6. Terms and Conditions

6.1 *Rights of CLIENT*

CLIENT reserves the right, in its sole discretion, to exercise any or all of the following rights and options at any time with respect to this RFI and any Submission:

- Reject any and all Responses, seek additional Responses, and enter into negotiations with one or more Respondents
- Determine the criteria for evaluating Responses in its sole judgment
- Use or incorporate the content of Responses into drafts of the PROGRAM-NAME Program Manual, evaluation framework, or other program materials without remuneration
- Cancel or withdraw this RFI
- Amend the terms, conditions and requirements of this RFI
- Conduct any investigations and inquiries it deems appropriate into the ability of a Respondent
- Retain independent consultants that CLIENT deems necessary to evaluate the Proposals
- Request clarification from a Respondent when in CLIENT's opinion, a Response requires further clarification
- Contact the references provided by the Respondent
- Select any or more than one Response for further negotiation, even if such Response or Responses do/es not provide the lowest prices
- CLIENT will retain copyright to all material created under this Project unless explicitly negotiated in writing

The successful Respondent will be required to sign a contract with CLIENT in which they accept responsibility for the performance of services as negotiated in a Statement of Work. A contract between the CLIENT and the selected vendor will be subject to and be in accordance with all Federal and Provincial laws as may be applicable.

6.2 *No Obligation*

CLIENT is not bound in any way upon the review of a Response. Further correspondence and communication between the Respondent will not legally impose any obligation upon CLIENT, and CLIENT will only be bound to a Respondent upon entering into an Agreement between the parties.

6.3 Withdrawal of Response

A Respondent may withdraw its Response at any time by notifying CLIENT in writing of its desire to withdraw.

6.4 Resubmitting Responses

Where a Respondent has withdrawn a Response, the Respondent may resubmit provided that it is received by CLIENT no later than the submission deadline.

6.5 Amendment to Responses

The Respondent may modify or amend a Response at any time prior to the Submission Deadline by submitting a replacement Response.

6.6 Accuracy

The information provided by CLIENT with respect to this RFI is provided solely for the purpose of assisting prospective Respondents with the submission of a Response, and does not purport to be all-inclusive or to contain all information that Respondents may require. In preparing a Response, Respondents should undertake their own investigations, and should consult their own advisors to verify the information contained in this RFI. The information provided in this RFI is provided as is, and CLIENT makes no representation or warranty or condition as to the accuracy or completeness of such information. CLIENT expressly disclaims any liability for any representations, warranties or conditions (express or implied) in connection with this RFI.

6.7 Costs for Preparing the RFI

CLIENT will not be responsible for reimbursing Respondents for any costs incurred in preparing and presenting a Response or otherwise in connection with this RFI. Furthermore, CLIENT will not be responsible for reimbursing Respondents for the use of any of their comments, suggestions and notes into program materials.

7 Response Template

Please copy this section and the next one (draft Statement of Work) into your main submission document. You may fill in the following template or use your own format.

Name of contact:

Phone number of contact:

Email address of contact:

Name of organizational entity:

Mailing address:

Web site:

Name of corporation that would take legal responsibility for the contract (if different from above):

Daily consultancy rates for the following roles (excl. taxes) if applicable for this project:

Principal consultant/researcher (10 years + experience):

Senior consultant/researcher (5 years + experience):

Consultant/researcher:

Administrative/technical support:

Name(s) and affiliations to be acknowledged as External Reviewer in Program Manual (maximum two names; if you would prefer us not to acknowledge you, please write N/A):

By submitting this Response you confirm that your comments and suggestions may be used and incorporated into program materials without payment.

References: Please provide contact information for three clients who can speak to your team's or organization's:

- Flexibility in revising project scope as the situation changes
- Ability to deliver on time and on budget
- Quality of your research and evaluation work
- Ability to work collaboratively with community-based organizations
- We will contact references for the three top-rated Respondents only.

Name of referee:

Job title:

Organization:

Phone number:

Email address:

Brief description of project(s) that you carried out for this client: (20 words or so is adequate)

Name of referee:

Job title:

Organization:

Phone number:

Email address:

Brief description of project(s):

Name of referee:

Job title:

Organization:

Phone number:

Email address:

Brief description of project(s):

8 Draft Statement of Work

Please copy this section into your main submission document along with the Response Template above, and use some way to highlight your changes and notes (e.g., track changes or another font). You may insert your comments into the body of the document and/or summarize your main points in a separate section.

This draft Statement of Work is provided to give Respondents a basis for planning and cost estimation, and to demonstrate to CLIENT how you would approach the project. If you are selected as one of the two or three Respondents who are invited to the next stage, you may revise the suggestions you make here.

8.1 Work Breakdown Structure of Overall Program

From the perspective of project management, PROGRAM-NAME has been broken down into Work Streams:

[LIST WORK STREAMS]

Each Work Stream has an 'owner' who is responsible for ensuring that the work packages are carried out successfully.

During the period covered by this contract, the Evaluator will lead (or 'own') Work Stream X: Monitoring & Evaluation. Specific tasks will be subject to revision as the Evaluation Plan is developed, and there will be occasional overlaps with other Work Streams.

Note that the Work Packages are not tied to specific dates, since many of them are recursive (e.g., monthly or ongoing). Deliverables and timelines are in the next section.

8.2 Work Breakdown Structure of Monitoring & Evaluation

LIST WBS

Details

Name of Activity	Description and Notes
4.1 Plan Work Stream	
4.1.1 Define work	Develop Evaluation Plan and define project scope, addressing overlaps with other Work Streams and how to resolve them. The Plan may be revised throughout the project to reflect changing needs if approved in writing by the Evaluator and CLIENT Senior Manager, Education.
4.2 Develop evaluation framework	
4.2.1 Refine program design & indicators	<p>Ensure that the program is informed by relevant evidence and is synchronized with the evaluation framework.</p> <p>This activity essentially means revising the draft Program Manual (which includes an evaluation framework and indicators) on the basis of the comments of external reviewers, the external consultant (to be hired in DATE), and the participating programs. The intent is to engage the Evaluator in a deep understanding of the program design and to ensure the program is evaluable. We hope that the revisions at this stage will be fairly minor.</p> <p>Further revisions of the Program Manual after DATE OTHER THAN the evaluation framework, indicators and measures will NOT be the responsibility of the Evaluators.</p>
4.2.2 Confirm data sources & costs if applicable	If the evaluation design includes data from external providers (e.g., health care utilization, CRA, school boards), confirm the costs and feasibility of using the data. The consent forms may need to be revised accordingly.
4.2.3 Develop a monthly/quarterly reporting template	Working with the project manager, create a template that can summarize program data monthly and quarterly. It would include satisfaction ratings, suggestions for improvements, etc. (see Deliverables below)
4.2.4 Develop data collection tools or processes	Work with CLIENT to create survey forms or other instruments
4.3 Collect data	
4.3.1 Create sampling & rollout methodology	Design a roll-out strategy for data collection so that improvements are made in waves.
4.3.2 Collect initial data &	Collect data from a pilot group, listen to complaints and suggestions,

feedback	then roll out to increasing numbers.
4.3.3 Analyze initial data & incorporate improvements	Revise data collection instruments and processes based on feedback
4.3.4 Collect data from all participating Clubs	At this point, the data collection should be primarily done by program staff as part of program processes and/or automatically derived by web analytics.
4.4 Analyze & report data	
4.4.1 Populate reporting template with available data	The first reports may contain dummy data, and gradually fill with real data as it is collected.
4.4.2 Test usefulness of report with users	Stakeholders and end users of the reports should be requested for feedback on how usable and valuable it is. Does it meet their requirements?
4.4.3 Revise reporting template	By the end of the first year, filling out the reporting template will be as streamlined and as automatic as possible.
4.4.4 Analyze collected data	Data will be analyzed at regular intervals to provide ongoing feedback to the program.
4.4.5 Prepare regular monitoring reports based on template	Monthly, quarterly reports; includes updates on evaluation activities. See Deliverables below.
4.5 Prepare annual evaluation reports	
4.5.1 Draft annual reports assessing the program	The annual PROGRAM-NAME evaluation cycle might be: May 30 - First draft of annual report circulated to stakeholders; June 30 - Second draft incorporating feedback from program locations and data from final surveys to make changes for following September; August 30 - Final draft submitted to the Program Sponsor. Timelines will need to be clarified in the Evaluation Plan.
4.5.2 Get external reviews of annual reports	Ask academic researchers and experts to review annual evaluation reports and incorporate their feedback into the annual cycle.
4.5.3 Update CLIENT evaluation framework with lessons learned	This project should contribute to or at least be consistent with the sponsoring agency's framework. The tools and templates arising from PROGRAM-NAME may be used by other CLIENT programs.

4.5.4 Prepare final evaluation report	See Deliverables below.
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8.3 *Timeline and Deliverables*

The following dates and deliverables will be refined during the development of the Evaluation Plan.

The overall period covered by this contract is DATE TO DATE.

Date	Deliverable	Notes
DATE	Revised Program Manual	The work involved in revising the Program Manual is expected to be minor, incorporating comments from reviewers and insights from the Evaluators.
DATE	Multi-year Evaluation Plan	The Evaluation Plan will lay out a Statement of Work for the first year and progressively less detail for subsequent years. The Plan will be updated annually to fill in the details for the upcoming year(s).
DATE	Data Instruments	Revision or development of data collection instruments and measures that, whenever possible, can be gathered unobtrusively or as an integrated part of program implementation.
Monthly, Quarterly	Data Reports	<p>Monthly reports will include feedback to program staff regarding youth satisfaction, suggestions for improvements, and other useful program data, including an update by the Evaluator showing progress against the Evaluation Plan.</p> <p>Quarterly reports will provide summaries requested by the Program Sponsor and the Project Manager.</p> <p>Much of the data collection may be carried out by program staff or automatically on the web site, with quality control audits by the Evaluator.</p>
MONTH YEAR, YEAR, YEAR	Annual evaluation report	<p>Annual report that evaluates the program and provides recommendations for the upcoming year, including revision of reporting template, measures and data collection tools.</p> <p>The final evaluation report will comprise a summative</p>

		assessment of the program's impact and cost-effectiveness, making policy recommendations for CLIENT, funders and other Canadian youth programs.
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8.4 *Cost assumptions*

As stated above, the expected budget for the Evaluation is \$85-\$100,000 per year starting in DATE. The budgets may vary by year. For example, the first year will involve a relatively small number of participants, but a heavy investment in the development and pilot testing of the program and evaluation framework. The final year will require additional analysis for a summative assessment of impact and cost-effectiveness.

CLIENT will provide French translation for program materials and surveys. If interviews with mentors and youth are carried out by Evaluators, the Evaluators are expected to have at least one person on their team who can interview francophone subjects.

CLIENT expects minimal travel requirements for Evaluators. Communication will be mainly via phone and email with program staff and mentors. Members of the Evaluation team may wish to visit local programs. If inter-city travel is required by your evaluation design, please include travel expenses within the budget range stated above.

If CLIENT requires travel, this will be discussed later.

CLIENT will assign administrative and technical support to the Evaluators where appropriate, to maximize cost efficiency. The Evaluators should comment on their requirements regarding the level of administrative support.

9 APPENDIX

9.1 *Expression of Interest*

On DATE, an invitation to submit Expressions of Interest was posted on the project opportunities board of the Canadian Evaluation Society, distributed to the YouthMentoring listserv, and emailed to several Evaluators known to CLIENT.

Expressions of Interest for evaluation of PROGRAM-NAME

CLIENT launched a [description of program] in DATE [add a couple of sentences of description here].

CLIENT is looking for an evaluation team to help them develop, improve and evaluate this program over the next x years. Their streamlined tendering process aims to provide value for the program while minimizing the cost of proposal development for applicants. The assignment would likely begin in DATE and involve an annual renewable contract.

If you are interested please respond to CONTACT-NAME, JOB-TITLE via email to CONTACT-EMAIL by

1:00pm Eastern Time DATE. Your email should include the following:

- Statement that you would like to receive the Request for Information for evaluation of CLIENT's PROGRAM-NAME.
- The name and web site of an entity or organization that would probably be willing to manage the evaluation contract and that has demonstrated expertise in the areas of Canadian educational or social service policy development and/or program evaluation. The entity may be a department of an academic institution, or a non-profit research institute, or a for-profit consulting firm, etc. At this point we are not requesting formal confirmation from the entity.
- Links to at least two relevant research or policy reports written by a prospective principal investigator (who could be you or a member of the organization that you're acting for) regarding secondary or post-secondary education, youth mentorship, after-school programs, and/or youth career development. We are asking for web links rather than attached documents because we are looking for engagement in knowledge transfer as well as research expertise.
- Bios, resumes or CVs of at least two senior investigators with relevant expertise who are available to work on the project. Relevant expertise must include experience in working with Canadian community-based organizations; a graduate degree in a relevant field; and publications in peer reviewed or public policy literature. Bios may be in the form of web links or attached documents.

Applicants may be individuals, teams or organizations. If the applicant is an individual, he or she must be affiliated with an organization that can take responsibility for delivering the terms of the contract.

CLIENT will select between five to ten applicants to receive a Request for Information based on the following criteria:

- Research, evaluation and/or policy expertise in the relevant subject areas
- Prominence and credibility in the relevant subject areas
- A commitment to and demonstrated engagement in knowledge transfer

If you wish clarification, please feel free to contact CONTACT-NAME at CONTACT-EMAIL before end of day DATE.